
DEVELOPMENT OF IDEAS RELATED TO THE HISTORY OF PEDAGOGY UNDER THE LEADERSHIP OF PROFESSOR O. ALEUOV

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Annotation. The article is about describing the formation of new pedagogical ideas, new directions for their development, conducting pedagogical research, updating the general pedagogical methodology necessary in educating the younger generation. The article analyzes the main directions of development of pedagogical thought in Karakalpakstan during the years of independence. The article also describes the works of Oserbay Aleuov, a scientist who made a great contribution to enriching the science of the history of pedagogy by analyzing the historical development of the Karakalpak people, the formation and development of views on education and upbringing in these historical conditions. The article provides information about the main trends and ideas in the development of pedagogical thought in the research works of Professor O. Aleuov, views on the study of the history of pedagogy, folk pedagogy and traditions.

Key words: pedagogy, history, reform, personnel, economics, teacher, equipment, technology, National, value, psychology, method.

INTRODUCTION. The development of ideas related to the history of pedagogy in this scientific team of Karakalpakstan, during the years of independence, research related to the history of pedagogy of the Karakalpak people was carried out in the college under the leadership of Professor O. Aleuovtyn, and a number of doctors of sciences and candidates of science received scientific works under the guidance of Professor O. Aleuovtyn, two candidates of sciences T. Utebaev, S. Khodzhanizayova received scientific works, as well as P. Abdimuratov, P. Palvanizayov, M. Khadzhiyeva, A. Dzhumabekova, K. Seitmuratov, A. Bekimbetova,

M. Aitimbetov, Yu. Purkhanov, A. Bekdzhanova, B. Arziyeva, E. Menlimuratova, M. Allayarov, A. Gurbanbaeva, E. Orazimbetov worked together. However, in Karakalpakstan, along with similar activities aimed at the development of pedagogical science, scientific research is needed. It should be said that the successful implementation of socio-economic reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan is associated with a multifaceted personnel issue [2]. Today's education is not only the transfer of data knowledge to students in the classroom, but also an educational theory, which is based on the experience accumulated and developed over the years, national humanistic abilities, pedagogical and psychological diagnostic methods, as well as a professional culture of conversation are the skills of a teacher, it is necessary to be human possessing the use of new pedagogy and information technology and experience. Young teachers receive advanced training at their place of education.

LITERATURE REVIEW. In the period 2012-2016. In the last three decades the field of science has begun to grow slightly. The reason is that the requirements of the one-stage doctoral program are a little cold for the implementation of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 28, 2012 No. 365 “On the development of a system for passing the certification of recent education and scientific and pedagogical personnel.” Utebaev T. Received the degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences in 2016. Like teachers, the desire to study and learn about the history and national development of the country did not develop on its own. This is related to teaching history. On the other hand, students of the history of pedagogy are interested in scientific news that is published monthly by academic teachers, and factual materials are directly related to the date of appearance of these materials by students. As a result of many years of scientific research, the study on the topic “Half of the 20th century of agriculture in Karakalpakstan - the development of educational ideas in the 21st century” discussed the scientific research of scientists who contributed to the development of science pedagogy. As a result, in 2016, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences O. Aleuov successfully defended his

doctoral dissertation on the topic “Half of the 20th century in Karakalpakstan - the development of educational ideas at the beginning of the 21st century.”

Research ideas related to the history of pedagogy in Karakalpakstan can be seen in the example of students. On December 29, 2016, with the decision of the Academic Council of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University, the certification commission under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan awarded T. Utebaev the academic degree of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences. T. Utebaev’s dissertation work is a methodological manual for students and school teachers [3].

The scientist T. Utebaev is known not only in Karakalpakstan, but also in neighboring countries; he is a scientist of social, philosophical and pedagogical ideas. Based on the results of his research work, more than 100 scientific projects have been supported. Among them are the monograph “Half of the 20th century of cultivation in Karakalpakstan - the development of educational thought at the beginning of the 21st century”, the textbook “Formation and development of pedagogical science in Karakalpakstan”, methodological guides “Pedagogical workshop: teaching, training and development”. To date, about 20 scientific articles have been published in foreign scientific journals, in the proceedings of scientific institutions in Germany, India, China, Moscow, Kazan, Voronezh, Kazakhstan, Aktobe, Turkestan.

Symposia, congresses and conferences devoted to international affairs expressed opinions and made scientific reports. The educational ideas and programs of the Karakalpak people have attracted the attention of people all over the world. For example, he visited the Almaty Castle of Kazakhstan and participated in some scientific presentations, while he was in the Geneva Castle of Switzerland, Russia and the countries of Kazakhstan, he took part in several international conferences online and expressed his thoughts. He also traveled to the Tashkent, Bukhara, Samarkand, Navoi, Urgench, Fergana, and Andijan fortresses and gave his scientific reports at scientific and theoretical conferences held throughout the republic. At these same scientific and theoretical conferences, his theses and articles were published in scientific collections and received certificates. This is clear evidence of the development of pedagogical thought in Karakalpakstan.

METHODOLOGY. Today, as a member of the Academic Council for awarding academic degrees, he will make a great contribution to the defense of dissertations at the Karakalpak State Pedagogical Institute, Karakalpak State University, and Urgench State University.

Pedagogical science is a social and humanitarian science, which is closely connected with society, the period of its development, changes from the point of view of the period and continues to develop. If we separate it from society, then we will find ourselves against the principle of the universal connection between the science of pedagogy and education. This will bring science to a standstill. Pedagogy is rich in the innovations of the era of impartiality, it is the normative and legal guardian of radical educational reform, and every part of the program has a special meaning. M. Aytimbetov “Development of the secondary education system of Karakalpakstan during the years of independence (late 20th century and early 21st century)” [4], studied the history of the development of higher education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan during the years of Independence by analyzing the authors. M. Aytimbetov’s research, turned to the materials of the republican archive, studied scientific pedagogical literature, regulatory documents, comparative pedagogical history, prognosis, statistical analysis, comparative interpretation, pedagogical research, using research methods, used research methods in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. M. Aytimbetov, in his scientific article, focused on the quality of education and explained the quality of the technology for monitoring the quality of education in higher educational institutions from the point of view of both self-assessment and self-development measures.

Apart from this research, it has a very important place in the development of the education system in higher education institutions, as well as the quality of education, as a scientific term in achieving efficiency. The reason for this is the improvement in the quality of education due to innovative ideas of reforms that are being carried out today in the system of lifelong education. Scientist Bakhtiyar Riza said: “The place of the teacher is at the door, in states where one turns away from knowledge, and the place of such states is outside.” Taking into account the regional, socio-cultural and

national mentality of Karakalpakstan, we are trying to determine the future of modern education, pre-training of teaching staff, modern requirements for education, and problems of teacher’s pedagogical skills. Researcher K. Seitmuratov looked into the history of Karakalpak modernism and managed to overcome new challenges. “Educational services of Seifugabit Mazhitova” [5]. Professor O. Aleuov began to analyze and demystify, to clarify the various forms of national awakening in Karakalpakstan at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries.

At the end of the twenties of the 20th century, science and polytechnic knowledge could not develop in a society that did not pay attention to the development of science and technology. And he emphasized the need for communication skills training. Several years ago, the pedagogical visions of K. Seitmuratov provided scientific and methodological tools aimed at current practice and use in the system of lifelong education. Methodologies such as: “Primer”, “Educational Book”, “Book for Adults” were written not only to improve children’s knowledge, but also to develop political knowledge. Therefore, in the lessons, a special place is given to understanding the importance of knowledge in the life of the individual and society, the importance of national identity, humanism, morality, physical and aesthetic culture. In his thoughts related to the theory of didactic views, the content of the didactic point of view, the content of the lesson materials, the level of knowledge and understanding, a living reflection of the lesson, the transition from the abstract to the concrete, from the practical to the constructive. In particular, teaching materials should be related to the topics being studied, children should be encouraged to think logically, increase their knowledge of left-hand traffic, follow the sequential principle in teaching, and use pictures in the lesson to improve their knowledge.

It is indicated that the teacher must adhere to the norms of politeness of students in their upbringing and education, children should count on receiving an example from the teacher, as well as the need to take into account the psychological characteristics of the child. In terms of education and training, children discover the world through play, the development of organizational abilities, manners, aesthetic

ideas, and even the social activity of children. Sociable children are formed by feelings of intelligence, friendship, cooperation, creativity. The teacher-scientist explains some ideas about the physical education of children, explains the influence of physical education on the free development of the body, improvement of mental activity, and mental state. The content of physical education classes includes exercise of the child's body, regular physical exercise, breathing and sleep, and important advice is given on the rules of hygiene for children during classes. In the process of research, U. Seitmuratov's ideas about the aesthetic education of the body were based on the experience of its artistic development. In works of art, the spiritual world of the body was shown through the development of the beauty of the world, as well as the educational impact on manners and politeness, its ability to organize, revive its good feelings, it is scientifically discussed, which provides an example of the importance of the call to purpose.

DISCUSSION. Researcher M. Khojaev, studied in the scientific publication of Professor O. Aleuovtyn “The spiritual and educational views of Khoja Ahmed Yassavid” [6], including morals are formed from the position of humanistic ideas in the works of sages.

At a time when Uzbekistan develops its nationalism, it becomes known to the world as a unique example of various aspects, the spiritual and educational views of Khoja Akhmet, the scientific interpretation of his thoughts at different levels of education, the influence of the form of modern man, also education outside the classroom, the study found some support. The reason is that the educational significance of the wisdom of Khoja Ahmed Yassawi is not fully realized today.

Although the wisdom of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi is undoubtedly important in human education and has shaken up the world of science, its special place in school education is not inferior to any discipline. Although 840 years separate us from Khoja Ahmed Yasawi, the educational ideas in his books are important pedagogy in our time, in the formation of such virtues as patriotism, humanity, self-control and friendship, as well as in serving the country without sparing effort. A. Bekimbetova in folk pedagogy of the Karakalpaks shows the development of programs for the

intellectual education of children, as well as the tools used in the current educational process [7]. In folk pedagogy, it is important to define the mind as a personality, and respect the human intellect as a sacred gift.

Attention is drawn to the fact that the mind is associated with the individual characteristics of each person. The body cannot be trained according to nature without molding the body from the mind, and special attention must be given to the service of mind and knowledge. It is for this reason that our people throughout human history have called for knowledge and science. In folk pedagogy, the process of understanding the world operates on the basis of information coming from human senses, human desire to understand the world, to discover its mysterious phenomena. They said that if the desire to understand the world is inherent in human nature, then a person cannot remain abstract in the world. Folk pedagogy comes to the practical conclusion that knowledge of the world depends on intuition, feelings (empiricism) and reason (rationalism), as well as everyday experiences (sensualism).

In folk pedagogy, children's games are widely used as a means of mental education, and “Riddle”, “Nine Circle”, “Stone” and other games are among the most effective games in the development of such phenomena as search, synthesis, comparison. In folk pedagogy, special attention is paid to intellectual education, arithmetic knowledge, and housekeeping. This knowledge is used to develop their logical and abstract thinking abilities. Folk pedagogy needs to form a correct understanding of the order of trace phenomena in the teaching system, the cause-and-effect relationship of bodies, the definition of quantitative and qualitative relationships, and the need for all movements in nature. Conducted on a certain regular basis.

A. Bekimbetova drew attention to the importance of astronomical knowledge in folk pedagogy, “Iron Pipe”, “Seven Pirates”, “Scales”, etc. Time, thanks to the repetition of the same movements, the relationship between the celestial bodies and the earth, the seasons of spring, summer, autumn, winter, moon, day, night, etc. Due to the lifestyle of people, the functioning of the production process has a significant impact on the development of the psyche. Human understanding of the world of

plants - botany, agriculture - veterinary medicine, weather - radio - hydrometeorology, calculation-book-mathematics, astrology-astronomy is the basis for the education of currently developed areas of knowledge. Our ancestors today were born into nature, so if they needed any level of experience, knowledge and life, they would have reached that level. This knowledge that our forefathers collected helps us stay employed in the domestic and commercial sectors in the current era.

CONCLUSION. In addition, programs for the intellectual education of the people are implemented in the same way as the dead houses, and this shows that it is of great importance in the spiritual development of youth. Based on the existing ideas, we, together with the editors, selected those ideas that were mentioned in articles on the history of pedagogy, which are related to the development of pedagogical ideas in impartiality volumes. Pedagogical science, as a social and humanitarian area, is closely connected with the period of its development, changes from the point of view of the period and continues to develop. If we separate him from public life, then we get a child who opposes the principle of the universal connection of pedagogical science with education. So, pedagogy is enriched by the innovations of the independence era, enriched and integrated with other areas of the modern world. Thus, enriching the current information flow in pedagogy, developing its scientific and theoretical apparatus, combining the educational process with computer science and information technology, etc. There are important issues in Karakalpakstan that are awaiting resolution in the implementation of the reform of the education system of the people of Karakalpakstan, taking into account the national mentality.

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